

3rd International Conference

Lakes and Reservoirs

Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology

24 - 26th September 2024, Gdańsk

Book of abstracts

Editors

Piotr Klimaszyk & Piotr Rzymiski

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The authors are responsible for the content of the abstracts.

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Dear Colleagues,

Reflecting a better understanding of inland waters as ecological systems, the aim of limnology is the integration of studies from the fields of physical, chemical, and biological research. Human activities and environmental changes generate novel avenues for scientific exploration, which is essential for the enhanced management of water resources; this is critical for sustainable development and the future of humanity if one considers the pivotal role these resources play.

With this in mind, the Polish Limnological Society organized the 3rd International Conference “Lakes & Reservoirs: Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology”, held from September 24th to September 26th, 2024, in the picturesque city of Gdańsk in Poland. The conference is organized in cooperation with the Romanian Limnogeographical Association and with the partnership of the University of Gdańsk under the honorary patronages of its Rector and Dean of the Faculty of Oceanography and Geography. Previous editions were also organized in Poland, first in 2016 (Iława, Warmia–Masuria, Poland) and second in 2019 (Mikorzyn, Greater Poland, Poland), and were attended by researchers from Europe, Asia, and South America.

The conference themes focus on emerging issues related to the ecology, complexity, and diversity of aquatic environments, their restoration and management, risk assessments, and control and mitigation measures. The subject of the presented works encompasses the effect of climate change on aquatic environments, analysis of emerging contaminants in surface waters, hydrology and management of lotic and lentic ecosystems, novel methods of lake restoration and river protection, and issues related to the invasion of alien aquatic species.

The conference includes plenary lectures by renowned experts, oral sessions, short communications, and a field scientific trip to Slovinski National Park.

Piotr Klimaszuk (Adam Mickiewicz University)

Reanata Augustyniak Tunowska (University of Warmia and Mazury)

Piotr Rzymiski (Poznan University of Medical Sciences)

Plenary lectures

Eutrophication and System Analysis Guided Lake Restoration: Examples from The Netherlands

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Nutrient pollution of inland waters – eutrophication – is the most widespread water quality issue all around the globe. Eutrophication is a wicked problem that often leads to harmful cyanobacterial blooms in lakes, ponds, and reservoirs, impairing ecosystem services. Main sources of nutrients are losses from (insufficiently treated) wastewater and from agricultural activities, while climate change is expected to further intensify ongoing eutrophication of inland waters.

Eutrophication also remains a key water quality concern for water management in the Netherlands, where in 50 % of the surface waters nutrient concentrations are too high to meet the Water Framework Directive (WFD) target of a good ecological condition. Eutrophication prevails despite decades of external nutrient control from point sources followed by additional ecosystem-oriented in-lake interventions, such as biomanipulation. The main reasons for the limited, temporary, or unsuccessful ecological improvement of Dutch lakes are diffuse sources of nutrient pollution, legacies in catchment soils and sediments, ecosystem alterations, incongruent policies, and inadequate interventions, sometimes even including application of magical methods without any scientific underpinnings. With the WFD deadline of 2027 approaching, water management and researchers are redesigning lake restoration practices because traditional approaches did not yield the desired outcomes. Currently, a system-analysis-based intervention package of multiple measures in which maintenance to keep a lake, pond or reservoir in a desired state is no longer undebatable.

I will present examples from several case studies in the Netherlands that implemented multiple measures simultaneously based on a lake system analysis. The interventions were tailored to the specific case, reduced the (external/internal) nutrient load effectively, and multiple in-lake measures aided in speeding up recovery and moving the lake into the desired state. Each case has thorough post-intervention monitoring, which allows evaluation of the intervention's effectiveness and duration, and facilitates decision if a maintenance intervention is required. Maintenance is a necessity in the Netherlands, where ongoing diffuse nutrient load remains. Maintenance will allow recreational activities and delivery of other ecosystem services and will be needed until decades after policies have been aligned and protecting the environment has become the top priority.

Lakes in the Anthropocene: Arctic ecosystems as sentinels of climatic and other environmental changes

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Arctic ecosystems are on the “frontline” of climate change, but due to a lack of direct long-term monitoring data, indirect approaches, such as paleolimnology, must be used to reconstruct missing data sets. A considerable amount of research has amassed over the last four decades on High Arctic limnology and paleolimnology (reviewed in my recent 2023 book: *Lakes in the Anthropocene: Reflections on tracking ecosystem change in the Arctic* - International Ecology Institute, Germany). Major ecosystem changes have been recorded, using primarily diatom-based paleolimnological records, throughout the circumpolar Arctic. For example, some of our earliest work focused on the paleolimnology of shallow, High Arctic ponds, where we recorded striking limnological changes linked to warming and reduced ice covers. Although our understanding of the responses of small to mid-sized Arctic lakes and ponds to recent climate warming has greatly increased over the last few decades, little is known on even the basic limnological conditions of Canada’s “Northern Great Lakes”. Using dated sediment profiles, we have assessed lake trajectories, over the last ~200 years, for Lake Hazen (Ellesmere Island, Nunavut), Great Bear Lake (Northwest Territories, NWT), and Great Slave Lake (NWT), and compare these to changes observed in medium and small-sized systems. Questions posed include: What were the baseline limnological states for these “Northern Great Lakes”? Has accelerated warming altered the algal communities of these large, deep Arctic lakes, and if so, how do trends compare among lakes? We have shown that these three Arctic giants share strikingly similar shifts in diatom composition and sedimentary chlorophyll *a* that reflect accelerated Arctic warming, rapidly declining ice covers and wind speed, and fundamental changes in lake thermal structure. A clear continuum of changes from shallow ponds to the very large lakes shows that key aquatic thresholds have been surpassed and that these ecosystems are now fundamentally different than they were just a few decades ago. These changes will undoubtedly cascade throughout the food web leading to changes important to local Indigenous populations and to the global community.

Baltic the sea of changes

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Baltic experienced in its short history (12 thousands years) profound changes between glacial lake, full saline open sea, freshwater warm lake and present day brackish sea. Recently this area went through episode of massive destruction through agricultural-based eutrophication, later recovery and now the very fast warming. As the state of the Baltic depends largely on riverine discharge, the quality of the rivers is of utmost importance for the state of this Sea. Exceptionally low, and salinity- controlled biodiversity of the Baltic is changing as well, with the important admixture of new coming species –often reported as “aliens”. Presentation reviews the recent models of Baltic evolution and propose a way to the adaptation to the ongoing changes.

Oral presentations

Application of PTR-MS and AAS techniques for the analysis of pollutants accumulated in lakes bottom sediments

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The bottom sediments of lakes are formed by the accumulation of material from soil erosion, weathering of rocks in the catchment area. In the sediments organic and inorganic chemicals from natural processes, including the dead remains of plant and animal organisms, are deposited. Also, it is the site of deposition of chemical compounds such as heavy metal salts supplied largely by human activities. The neighborhood of a city for a lake is usually unfavorable. The construction of cities, industrial or agricultural development results in the delivery of pollutants to the bottom sediments. Among anthropogenic pollutants, heavy metals and synthetic organic compounds, which are now widely used, as well as their decomposition products, occupy a special place. Heavy metals are commonly used by urban residents in various areas related to the use of modern technologies such as electronic products, transportation, the use of metal alloys and modern materials.

In 2021, bottom sediment samples were taken from four lakes located near cities. Each of these lakes is intensively used by the nearby human population. Łazienkowskie and Rychnowskie lakes are located near the city of Człuchów, Lake Jeleń near the city of Bytów, and Lubowidz Lake near the city of Lębork. In the sediment samples, the occurrence of heavy metals such as Cd, Cu, Fe, Ni, Mn, Pb, Zn was analyzed using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS - F). Also, the concentrations of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted from bottom sediments were investigated using a soft ionization mass spectrometer via proton transfer reaction (PTR - MS). Statistical analyses were performed, including multivariate cluster analysis and PCA. The analyses showed that bottom sediments from the studied lakes differed in terms of heavy metals present as well as VOCs emitted and the influence of anthropogenic pollutants.

Phosphorus fractions in the sediment of the meromictic lake, restored by P inactivation (Klasztorne Małe Lake, Kashubian Lakeland, Poland)

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Klasztorne Małe Lake (area 13.7 ha, max depth 20 m) is the third lake in the lake-river system, which is located in Kartuszy city. Since the second half of the 20th century, this water body was severely polluted by raw domestic and industrial wastewater, including sewage from nearby hospital. The water inflow from heavily polluted Karczemne Lake was an additional source of nutrients as well. Serious pollution led to changing a water mixing type from bradimictic into meromictic, but the meromixis acted as a protective barrier against the effects of the possible internal loading phenomenon from the monimolimnion zone.

Several restoration methods were implemented on Klasztorne Małe Lake. In 80s of the past century, the lake was artificially aerated, and in 2006 the first attempt of phosphorus inactivation using Phoslock® was made. Those restoration attempts did not bring the expected improvement in water quality due to the lack of raw sewage inflow elimination.

After the modernization of the sewerage system in the city and the elimination of the main external pollution sources, in 2021 and 2022 P inactivation using iron and aluminum chlorides (PIX 111 and PAX 18) was implemented on the lake.

The samples for P fractions analysis were taken at one research station, located at the deepest point of the lake (monimolimnion zone). 10-cm thick undisturbed sediment cores, taken at the research station, were immediately divided into two layers (5-cm thick) and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

Phosphorus fractionation performed in 2019 and 2020 (before restoration) showed, that amounts of TP in the bottom sediments of Klasztorne Małe Lake ranged from 6.415 mg P/g DW up to 7.948 mg P/g DW. P in the surface layer of the analyzed sediments was associated mainly with organic matter in the form of the moderately bioavailable NaOH-nrP fraction. In 2023, after the restoration completion, the amounts of TP in sediments were higher and ranged from 7.709 mg P/g DW. in the 5-10 cm layer in spring up to 9.828 mg P/g DW in the 0-5 cm layer. The quantitatively dominant fraction was NaOH-rP (53.9%TP in the 0-5 cm layer). The changes occurring in the water-bottom sediments interface of the studied lake during P inactivation and after its completion were quite dynamic, hence longer monitoring studies are needed to assess the effects of restoration.

The runoff modelling in catchment area using NRCS – CN method

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This paper considers the Soil Conservation Service curve number (SCS-CN) method with the spatial database based on GIS for the calculation of the discharge from the catchment of Pogăniş River. The Pogăniş River, the main water course in this basin, it's springs in the Semenic Mountains and flows into the Timiş River, having approximately 97 km. The curve number method was used to estimate runoff depth for this watershed based on soil hydrologic groups, land use and hydrological condition. The modelling was simulated for the period 11 – 22 July 2020, and the results were compared with the observed discharge. The algorithm percent-adjusts CN values and generates new layers for calibrated CN and S, essential for calculating cumulative infiltration through calibration. After running the model, the simulated peak flow is close to the observed discharge, but the response time of the catchment to the rainfall amounts input to the model is much shorter than the observed time. The HEC-HMS software is one for hydrological modelling, mainly used for the simulation of rainfall-runoff phenomena so useful and necessary in the design and reduction of flood risk.

Effects of climate change on ice cover in lakes in Europe – future scenarios

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Climate change represents one of the most important threats for global lake ecosystems. Lakes are a very critical natural resource that are sensitive to these changes. (Iestyn Woolwa R., 2020; ACIA 2004). Air temperature is considered to be the dominant variable driving lake-ice phenology (Williams S.G. and Stefan H.G., 2006; Miętus M. 2006). Global surface air temperature has increased by close to 1.3°C since the pre-industrial era. The average rate of temperature increase, according to ERA5, is 0.20°C per decade from 1979 to 2023 (Copernicus, 2024).

The expected effects of climate change will affect most of the physical parameters of lakes, including also the duration and thickness of ice cover (Rosenzweig C., 2007; Dibike Y. et al. 2024). The aim of this speech is to present selected effects of climate change on ice cover and introduce the impacts of climate change on the duration of ice cover on lakes in Europe. The outlined scenarios are developed for the years 2071-2100 and are based on daily averages of air temperature obtained from high resolution climate change scenarios prepared by the PRUDENCE project (Nöges T. et al. 2009).

According to Nöges T. et al. 2009 there will be a noticeable increase in European winter temperatures accompanied by a visible extension of the ice-free period. The largest ecological changes will be expected in lakes, which at present have ice cover in most winters and will be mostly not covered by ice in the future. It is predicted the regions in Europe, which will experience the biggest and most significant changes in ice cover duration ('hot spots') will extend from Central to Eastern Europe.

To sum up, lakes are regulators of environmental change, the understanding of their resistance, resilience, and responses to environmental change is crucial to their effective management (Williamson C.E. et al., 2009; Sommaruga R.; 2001). Developing models/scenarios concerning physical characteristic of lakes in Europe are very crucial to develop climate change impact indicators on ecological water quality of lakes (Nöges T. et al. 2009).

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Community-level response of benthic algae to environmental constraints in a riverine network using different identification approaches

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Rivers face numerous anthropogenic threats, including pollution and habitat destruction. Algae and especially diatoms serve as vital bioindicators in freshwater ecosystems providing information about ecological status. The microscopy analysis of benthic algae provides a broad view of multiple algal groups, offering a comprehensive overview of the community, but often falls short of species-level identification. On the other hand, the microscopy analysis of cleaned permanent diatom slides allows for detailed species-level identification of diatoms. DNA metabarcoding targeting diatoms with specific marker gene offers a very fine taxonomic resolution, providing detailed insights into diatom diversity and composition. However, its accuracy depends on, among other factors, the completeness and quality of the reference databases.

The objective of the study is to recognize which approach explains the best how environmental variables shape benthic algal communities in the studied riverine network.

130 samples from 67 sites in Hungarian watercourses were taken in August and September 2018, and in May and June 2019. Environmental variables were measured in situ (river width, velocity, temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen concentration, oxygen saturation, and pH) and in the laboratory (nutrients, chloride, soluble reactive silica, carbonate, bicarbonate, and chemical oxygen demand). Periphyton samples were collected from the most common substrate. Subsamples were then separated and preserved for further analyses. Subsamples preserved in Lugol's solution were analyzed by an inverted microscope to identify all algal groups. Other subsamples were cleaned by removing all organic material to prepare permanent diatom slides from which diatoms were identified to species level. For the molecular analysis, DNA was extracted from the subsamples and a short, 312 bp fragment of the *rbcL* gene was used for PCR amplification and metabarcoding. Important differences have been found within the three methods regarding taxa composition and diversity. Each approach enlightened different aspects of how the environment shapes benthic algal communities. While DNA metabarcoding enlightens hidden diversity within diatoms with potentially differing ecological preferences, a general view on the entire algal assemblage is also important.

*Hungarian National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NRDI) - FK146760
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Implementing Restoration Works on Degraded Peatlands from North-Western Romania

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The current context of adaptation to climate change and the actions to combat associated with biodiversity loss, are current challenges included in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development through objectives 13 (*Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*) and 15 (*Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss*). Peatlands are one of the most important carbon sinkers deposits and they have to be protected on long-term for their unique biodiversity species. Thus, within the RO-Environment program, a number of degraded peatlands were identified at national level, which require corrective interventions through specific restoration works. The implementation of these works was carried out within the NWPEAT project (Restoration of wetlands and peatlands in the Nord-West Region) managed by Babeş-Bolyai University and Norwegian Institute for Nature Research. The objectives proposed by the project aimed: improving the ecological status of habitats associated with efficient restoration works; raising target group awareness on the peatland ecosystem conservation and improving geographical information tools for decision-makers. The most relevant restoration works were oriented on reducing water-loss from peatland surface by stopping the drainage with natural dams positioned on the old ditches created in the past. In order to certify the potential progress of maintaining an optimum water budget in the peatlands we have consider installing a network of data loggers to monitor the level changes of underground waters. For reducing the impact of intense grazing, we have built wood fences around the peatlands to limit the transit or access of sheep and cattle inside the peatlands. The reduction of destructive anthropogenic interventions was achieved through an extensive process of raising awareness at the level of the local public on the ecosystem services provided by peatlands. Thus, tourist information panels were placed, indicating arrows for the identification and travel of some guided routes, building of some thematic paths, the online promotion of the actions and objectives proposed by the project.

Source of funding The study is associated with the project „Restoration of wetlands and peatlands in the North-West Region” (NWPEAT), implemented through the Programme „Environment, Climate Change Adaptation and Ecosystems” - RO-Environment, Call for Proposals Wetland and Peatland Restoration and is funded through the European Economic Area EEA Financial Mechanism 2014-2021.

Evaluation of the relationships between the water circulation system and the state of the ecosystems in the Razim-Sinoie Lake Complex

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The lake complex Razim-Sinoie is located in the north-western area of Dobrogea, southern to the Danube Delta and on the coastline of the Black Sea, being the largest stretch of water in Romania. The lakes are linked to the Sf. Gheorghe Branch (in the north) by numerous channels and backwaters being separated by a few alignments of poorly consolidated small-height marine sand bars. All these characteristics offer numerous features to the lake ecosystem which are reflected by the hydrological, thermal, dynamic, hydrochemical, and hydrobiological regime. The evolution of the lakes is connected to the water circulation system, the link with the Sf. Gheorghe Branch and the discharge of the waters in the Black Sea. These are the reasons why three main stages of the hydrological regime can be identified: I) in 1925 when the lakes had a natural regime; II) from 1925 to 1970 when there was a semi-natural regime due to the construction of the linking channels to the Sf. Gheorghe Branch; III) in 1970 when the accumulation of a larger volume of water for irrigation was sought. In the third stage (after 1970), the linking channels were deepened, and the second and the fifth channels that allowed the transfer to lake Sinoie, were built: Gura Portita was closed and the water transfer to the Black Sea was controlled only through the Lake Sinoie. These changes led to the increase of average water levels of the lake Sinoie, from +48 cm above Black Sea Level (aBSL) before 1970 to +70 cm aBSL between 1970 and 1996 which modified the amplitude of the average monthly values by more than 30 cm. The gradual increase of the levels and the accumulations of a larger volume of freshwater induced a major change in the salinity, especially in the Razim and Golovita lakes, which consisted in a gradual decrease from 7.8 g/l in 1925 to 2 g/l in 1951 and 0.4-0.6 g/l after 1970. At the same time, the nitrogen values risen gradually from 0.013-0.104 mg/l before 1970 to 2-2.5 mg/l between 1981 and 1990 or 3.3 mg/l in 1994, being closely related to those in the Sf. Gheorghe Branch. The level increase and salinity decrease led to a change in the hydro-biological characteristics by reducing the number of species and the rise in biological productivity. The evolution of the spatial distribution and abundance of phytoplankton and zoo-plankton associations have been correlated with the hydrological regime and the trophic level of the lakes.

Stable isotope analysis reveals diet niche partitioning between native species and the invasive black bullhead (*Ameiurus melas*)

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Introduction and spread of alien fish species pose a major threat to native communities and ecosystem functioning in freshwaters. Black bullhead is one of the most successful invaders in European waters with several detrimental effects on native biota and ecosystems. In this study, we used stable isotope analysis to compare the body size and season-dependent diet, trophic position, isotopic niche size, and niche overlap of the invasive black bullhead with two native fish species (roach and European perch) in Lake Balaton, Hungary. We found that black bullhead could be characterized by invertivore-piscivorous feeding habit with a high rate of fish consumption. The rate of fish predation by invasive black bullhead increased with body size, while no seasonal differences were observed in fish consumption. Contrary to our hypothesis, little evidence of actual feeding competition was found between black bullhead and native fishes. Our results suggest that the studied species assimilate distinct energy resources in different proportions leading to a substantial amount of niche partitioning among them. We conclude that black bullhead may represent a threat for native, small-sized fishes primarily through predation and recommend urgent management actions (e.g. selective removal of the species) to minimize its adverse impacts on native communities.

How do road crossings affect the functional diversity of aquatic macroinvertebrates?

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Functional diversity is regarded as a key component in understanding the link between ecosystem function and biodiversity, and is therefore widely investigated in relation to human-induced impacts. However, information on how the intersection of roads and streams (hereafter road crossings, representing a widespread habitat transformation in relation to human development), influences the functional diversity of stream-dwelling macroinvertebrates is still missing. The general aim of our study was to provide a comprehensible picture on the impacts of road crossing structures on multiple facets of the functional diversity of stream-dwelling macroinvertebrates. Our research showed that road crossing structures had negative impacts on functional richness and dispersion; i.e., functional diversification. However, we found no significant impact on functional divergence and evenness components. We found a decrease in functional redundancy at road crossing structures. This indicates a reduced ability of the community to recover from disturbances. Finally, we found that road crossings drive stream habitat and hydrological changes in parallel with modification of the trait composition of stream-dwelling macroinvertebrate assemblages. All these results suggest that road crossings cause notable changes in the functional diversity of stream-dwelling macroinvertebrate assemblages.

Response of zooplankton network indicators to land use in a river catchment

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Land use forms can significantly impact interspecies interactions in aquatic ecosystems. We tested the hypothesis that catchment management distinctly influences the dynamics, significance, and types of relationships within the zooplankton community structure of a postglacial river (northern Poland). Zooplankton interspecies interactions were assessed using network graph modeling across four diverse catchment sections: natural (NAT), urban (URB), urban/agricultural (URB/AGR), and agricultural (AGR). The NAT network was the most cohesive, dominated by taxa feeding on various food sources (*Asplanchna priodonta*, *Testudinella patina*, *Chydorus sphaericus*, *Thermocyclops crassus*), with balanced positive and negative interactions, what sign of ecosystem balance and resistance. The intensification of urban and agricultural pressures led to a weakening of the strength and significance of negative interspecies relationships, causing decentralization of the URB and AGR networks. Small, common bacterio-detritophagous and actively feeding rotifers (*Filinia terminalis*, *Anuraeopsis fissa*, *Polyarthra longiremis*) played a key nodal role there, which indicates homogenization and reduced ecosystem resistance. The graph layout highlighting connected components allowed us to observe the environmental filtering process between the studied sections, identifying phenomena of adaptation, or elimination of zooplankton species. This study provides an innovative approach to understanding the functioning of biotic structures in rivers and underscores the importance of sustainable management strategies of river basins undergoing urbanization and agricultural expansion.

The influence of restoration techniques on the environmental conditions of Lake Klasztorne Małe in Kartuzy

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As a result of transforming the catchment area into agricultural, urbanized, or industrialized areas, as well as discharging various types of sewage into lake waters, the eutrophication process rapidly accelerates and the natural water chemistry is significantly deformed. The most visible effects of lake water pollution are blooms of phytoplankton and cyanobacteria, deoxidation of bottom waters, and the initiation of the process of internal supply of N and P from bottom sediments. As a result, the economic and natural functions previously performed by lakes are limited. In cases of a high degree of lake pollution, an appropriately selected recultivation method should be implemented. One of the most popular, cheap, and effective methods of removing phosphates from the water is their chemical inactivation using iron, aluminum, calcium, and even magnesium salts.

Lake Klasztorne Małe is a meromictic water body, with a depth of 20.0 m and an area of 13.7 ha, which was restored by the phosphorus inactivation method.

Research carried out in 2023 showed that in the lake water, phosphates occurred in concentrations ranging between 0.001 and 0.032 mg P /L. It should be emphasized that before restoration, phosphate concentrations in the bottom layers of lake water exceeded 16 mg P/L. In 2023, the TP content at the bottom did not exceed 0.270 mg P/L, while before recultivation it reached 20 mg P/L. In 2023, there was a 95% decrease in the content of phosphates and a 74% reduction in the amount of total phosphorus in the surface layer of lake water compared to the values recorded before restoration. In turn, in bottom waters, the reduction of both phosphates and total phosphorus under the influence of PAX 111 and PAX 18 application was over 99%. In the water of the studied lake, the TN content varied from 0.89 mg N/L to 9.85 mg N/L. Vertical stratification was observed in the occurrence of total nitrogen, with the value increasing towards the bottom. Before recultivation, total nitrogen concentrations reached 65 mg N/L. Reducing the availability of biogenic compounds in lake waters limited primary production processes. Compared to the period before recultivation, a constant improvement in light conditions in the reservoir is currently observed, as evidenced by an increase in water transparency and a decrease in chlorophyll a concentration. The maximum visibility of the Secchi disc was 2.0 m.

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The impact of pharmaceutical pollution and elevated temperature on freshwater mussels

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The global use of pharmaceuticals is systematically rising and over the past few decades, they have become a new type of environmental pollutant. Antidepressants are a class of pharmaceuticals used to treat major depressive disorder, anxiety disorders, chronic pain, and addiction. Considering the progressive development of medicine and the demand for drugs, it is expected that their concentrations in water will increase and therefore influence aquatic biota, posing a threat to ecosystem structure and functioning. Simultaneously, lake water temperatures are expected to increase by 3-4°C by the end of the twenty-first century (IPCC). Such an increase in temperature could alter the toxicity of chemicals present in water through changes in bioavailability, and absorption.

Mussels are particularly sensitive to environmental disturbances due to their unique filter-feeding behaviours and sedentary life cycles. They typically keep their shells open to breathe and filter suspended matter from the water, but in stress conditions, they would close the shells, and decrease their activity.

In this study we aimed to analyze the effects of fluoxetine (selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor; SSRI) on the filtering behavior of freshwater mussel *Unio tumidus* Philipsson, 1788 (Bivalvia: Unionidae). Experiments were conducted in two thermal regimes (optimal and elevated temperature): 17°C, and 20°C respectively. The following concentrations of fluoxetine were used: 100 ng/L, 1 µg/L, 10 µg/L, and 100 µg/L.

The obtained results give a better understanding of mussels' responses to antidepressant water pollution. Including elevated temperature as an additional stressor, gives insight into future climate scenarios, which is crucial to identifying effective conservation and environmental management practices.

Phytool v3 reference library for the taxonomic and trait assignment of phytoplankton 23S rRNA barcodes

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DNA metabarcoding and trait-based approaches are two cutting-edge fields in ecological research and bioassessment, few studies yet focus on merging these approaches and enhance the potential of metabarcoding beyond taxonomic identification. Developing and using a reference barcoding library (Phytool v3), containing taxonomic and trait information on phytoplankton 23S rRNA barcodes, this study provides elements of answers to this field of investigation. Our goal was to (i) integrate trait assignment into the DADA2 bioinformatic pipeline so that traits can be directly assigned to ASVs and (ii) estimate the relevance of trait-based assignment in assessing the structure of environmental communities. To complete the first objective, an *in silico* validation test on the Phytool library was carried out. We found that a higher proportion of sequences could be assigned to traits than at fine taxonomic resolutions (i.e., genus or species). We also found that traits exhibiting good phylogenetic signals have good assignment of sequences. For the second objective, an environmental assessment was carried out. We hypothesized and concluded that assigning traits to ASVs from environmental samples yield meaningful and interpretable results on how communities are shaped in the four large peri-alpine lakes in France: Lakes Geneva, Annecy, Bourget, Aiguebelette, that were sampled over a year every month and the dynamics observed with traits and taxonomic data were compared.

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Biological and chemical diversity of arctic ponds in Svalbard

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Arctic freshwater ecosystems are considered to be relatively unpolluted. Ponds and lakes are low fertile and species-poor due to low direct human impact, extreme seasonality and harsh environmental conditions. On the other hand, of all the sites in the Arctic, Svalbard is one of the areas most affected by anthropogenic pollution that results from mining industry, atmospheric pollution transport and tourism. Also, climate warming affecting Svalbard with great force is disrupting the structure of terrestrial and aquatic biocoenoses.

We present the results of research conducted on 14 Arctic ponds differentiated by location and human impact. Among all, 4 ponds are located on the to Sven glacier hummocky moraine, 4 ponds close to the pristine tidal flat in Petuniabukta, 4 ponds close to tidal flat in vicinity of Longyearbyen and 2 ponds within old mining settlement Pyramiden. All examined ecosystems, except for four ponds situated near the glacier, are affected by flocks of waterbirds. Thegeese droppings, which are rich in nitrogen and phosphorus, pile up on the ponds banks.

Studies show that the water of all ponds is characterized by a slightly alkaline pH and relatively high electrolytic conductivity. This is a reflection of the geological structure of the land. Significant differences in nutrients and other chemical elements concentration were noted even between water bodies located close to each other. The chemical differentiation of the ponds within each group was comparable to variation between groups. No direct correlation was observed between the fertility of the ponds and the human impact or geese pressure. This indicates a strong influence of local (often in microscale) hydrological and catchment conditions on the functioning of the studied ponds.

A high taxonomic differentiation of zoo- and phytoplankton was found between the ponds, even despite their close proximity and similarity of catchment conditions and water chemical properties.

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Possibilities of assessing ice phenomena on lakes on the example of Lake Śniardwy

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Ice formation on rivers and lakes is a typical phenomenon of our geographical latitude, seasonal in nature, and a sensitive indicator of climate change. Their occurrence is important for the ecology of lakes, shaping the course of physical, chemical, and biological processes in the lake, and their reduction may in consequence lead to an increase in productivity and a deterioration in the water's trophic state. In Poland, observations of ice phenomena are conducted on selected lakes by the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute, and the first such observations were started at the turn of the previous century. The large-scale automation of the measurement and observation network in Poland in recent years has made it necessary to use other methods of assessing ice phenomena in order to preserve the existing data series.

The currently developed method of automating the monitoring of ice phenomena on lakes assumes the possibility of conducting observations in a stationary manner at selected representative points based on images from cameras and using mobile devices such as drones or satellites. The use of various imaging techniques for the phenomenon under study is being considered: optical, radar, or thermal imaging devices. Each modality has a different range of imaging capabilities and information provision (spatial and temporal resolution, measured ice parameters). Comparison of images from selected media provides the opportunity to verify the measurements and recommend the methods best suited to the needs and possibilities.

Lake Śniardwy is the largest lake in Poland located in the Land of the Great Masurian Lakes. It is a typical moraine lake characterized by a large surface area, shallow depth, developed shoreline, and gentle shores. Observations of ice phenomena on this lake have been made since 1971, but due to the automation of observations, the data sequence ends in 2021. The presented research attempts to implement the considered methods of automatic monitoring of ice phenomena in the years when manual observations were discontinued.

An attempt to use satellite data to calculate lake evaporation – case study from Northern Poland

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Evaporation is a component of the water balance of lakes that is currently attracting increasing interest. This is a consequence of the changing climate and the intense increase in air temperature observed in recent years, combined with a decrease in atmospheric humidity. The values of actual evaporation from lakes surface is measured using the evaporimeter rafts. In Poland, these measurements are made only in the warm half-year on four lakes. The starting point of the conducted research was the search for new methods of calculating lake evaporation, which would allow estimating the amount of evaporation for a particular lake when instrumental measurements are not carried out on it.

The evapotranspiration (ET) product provided by EUMETSAT Land SAF and the Evaporation from open water surfaces excluding oceans product provided by ERA5- (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store) were used for the analyses. The values of evaporation from lakes surface was calculated for the cool half-year using the Konstantinov method. For the warm half-year, evaporation values from the nearest evaporimeter rafts (GGI 3000) and evaporimeter pans were used and extrapolated for the lake. These values were compared with evaporation values calculated from satellite data. The correlation coefficient shows a strong relationship between the two values ($R^2 > 0.8$). Three regression models were used for further analyses: linear, Huber Regressor, Bayesian Ridge Regression. For their verification, the results obtained were compared with evaporation values calculated for the selected lakes.

The study provided an answer to the question of whether it is possible to use satellite data to determine evaporation from lake surfaces. It also made it possible to create a models for calculating evaporation from lake surfaces for which there are no instrumental measurements. In addition, it was shown that the relationship between the analysed variables could form the basis for a universal product.

Assessment of water quality in small water reservoirs in urban areas

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Small water reservoirs are subject to very strong anthropogenic pressure, which leads to their degradation. The aim of this study was to assess water quality in small water reservoirs located in urban areas. The study covered small water reservoirs of various origin and spatial development stage located in Toruń and Bydgoszcz (northern Poland). The analyses covered selected physicochemical parameters such as water temperature, conductivity, and ion concentrations of Cl, SO₄, HCO₃, Ca, Mg, Na, K, NO₃, NH₄, and PO₄. The study showed that water bodies located in the built-up part of the city exhibit higher ion concentrations and are subject to greater anthropopression.

Microplastic contamination of small water bodies: a reflection of their watershed characteristics?

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In Europe in 2018, almost half of all plastic waste found in the environment was, at the time of manufacture, intended for single-use only. These are generally used as food packaging, and recycling is still minimal (less than 30%). Once in the environment, they follow the same transfer pathways as many other plastic wastes, and are transported from land to water bodies, via small rivers. During their journey, these elements (more or less coarse) gradually break up under the effect of biotic and abiotic processes, until they reach sizes ranging from a few centimetres to a few tens of micrometres. These particles, generally between 0.1 and 5000 µm in size, are known as MicroPlastics (MP).

Although MP were of particular interest in marine ecosystems relatively early on (the first studies date back to the 1970s), it is only in 2011 that they are being studied in continental waters, and more specifically in rivers. However, sampled rivers are rarely the small streams at the base of hydrographic networks (difficult to access, intermittent), even though they represent particularly active transfer zones. Ponds and other small lentic water bodies, are even less represented in the sampled sites. Yet they occupy areas that are likely to emit large quantities of plastics (agricultural activities, road traffic). Although they can, according to some studies and on a global scale, represent a cumulative volume of water greater than that of large lakes, the contamination of these hydrosystems has rarely been assessed. It has even less often been related to the characteristics of the watershed (land use, activities).

Our study focused on various French ponds and reservoirs (Small Water Bodies, SWB), generally at the head of watersheds, with a variety of catchment areas (both in terms of surface area, land use and activities). Since 2022, we have been using a standardized protocol to determine the average concentration of MP in the water column. Each sample has been inspected under a stereomicroscope and each MP has been counted and listed. Our study provides new environmental data and is of particular interest, not only for the study of MP occurrence in these SWB, but also for their interaction with their catchment areas. It is therefore important to continue research into these small lentic systems, which are so prevalent throughout France and Europe.

The effects of restoration have passed - what's next? A case study of small eutrophied urban lake.

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Domowe Małe Lake in Szczytno (Masurian Lake District) has been degraded as a result of many years of anthropogenic pressure. Due to small water resources (area 11.8 ha, max. depth 4.9 m) and constant inflow of pollutants (municipal and rainwater sewage, waterfowl colonies, strong fishing pressure), at the end of the last century the lake became turbid with massive blooms of cyanobacteria. The first protective measure in the catchment area was the construction of a band collector that eliminated most of the rainwater inflows. Then, in the years 2010-2012, phosphorus inactivation was used using aluminum and iron coagulants. The effect of improving water quality lasted about 10 years, after which the symptoms of eutrophication returned to the pre-restoration level. An additional factor intensifying the decline in the clear water state is the current water deficit in the lake. For several years, the region has been struggling with hydrological drought, and the result of these phenomena is a drastic decrease in water levels in lakes. Over the last 5 years, Lake Domowe Małe has lost about 31% of its water resources, lowering the water table by one meter. Based on many years of environmental monitoring, the need to continue restoration activities was formulated, but after rebuilding the water balance. The concept of remedial actions assumes the reconstruction of the rainwater drainage system and the return (retention) of rainwater to the lake after its prior treatment in mechanical-chemical-hydrophyte treatment plants located on the inflow collectors. Next, the lake will be restored using the bottom sediment capping method combined with phosphorus inactivation, biomanipulation of macrophytes and fish, and selective discharge of future excess water using the Olszewski method.

Investigation of a landslide-triggered debris flow and dam formation in the Eastern Carpathians, Romania

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In the flysch belt of the Eastern Carpathians (Romania), most landslides triggering debris flows occur in remote locations and usually do not pose a significant hazard. However, some debris flow-slide events have impacted road infrastructure and caused extensive forest destruction, with a moderate impact on the local economy. In some cases, the debris fan deposits lead to the formation of temporary water accumulations behind dams. One of the most recent landslide and weather-induced debris flow events occurred in the summer of 2010, in the upper Iapa valley, a right tributary of the Bistrița River. Initially starting as a landslide process near the top of the Goșmanu-Geamăna Massif (Tarcău Mountains) at an elevation of 875 m a.s.l., the debris flow deposits obstructed a 300-meter section of the Iapa watercourse at 615 m a.s.l., forming a 10 m depth lake, currently known as Făgețel Lake. The main trigger was the heavy rains that impacted the entire region during the May-July period of 2010, but the high density of the forest paths and extensive deforestation in the logging area also have a significant contribution to the geomorphological processes that affect the southern slope of the Drumul Chinezilor ridge. However, the most interesting aspect related to the Iapa landslide-triggered debris flow is that of more than 20 large landslide dams formed due to extreme hydro-climate conditions in the Eastern Carpathians; this event is the singular one that has formed a long-term lake (more than 10 years) due to a debris flow-slide dam. This study compiles the climatic, anthropogenic, geological, and geomorphological evidence gathered during the field investigation in October 2023 and utilizes Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) data collected to reconstruct the occurred debris flow-slide event. Additionally, it explores considerations regarding the reactivation of landslide processes, dam stability, and the future evolution of the impounded lake (Făgețel Lake). Furthermore, the lessons learned and future actions required to prevent further mass movement associated with debris flow-slide processes in prone areas of the Eastern Carpathians are discussed.

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**Benthic invertebrates structure, with emphasis
on Ephemeroptera as bioindicators, against environmental
conditions (water quality, bottom sediments,
submerged macrophytes) in a shallow urban pond**

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Urban ponds contribute a great deal to the biodiversity at a regional level, being a crucial element of green and blue network in the urban matrix. Their primary function is to provide specific services such as water purification and flow regulation (stormwater ponds), sediment trapping, aesthetic value, environmental education, leisure activities such as boating and fishing. At the same time, they contribute to the freshwater biodiversity conservation in areas providing multiple pressures for water ecosystems like pollution, drying or invasive species. Thus, the recognition of their role as refuges in adverse conditions on neighbouring area is important for future conservation management. Studies of shallow urban pond adjacent to Adam Mickiewicz University Campus at Morasko in Poznań, Poland aim at the assessment of its biodiversity in terms of benthic organisms and macrophytes with relation to environmental conditions as water quality, bottom sediments composition as well as the management of the watershed area. Conducted studies revealed slightly eutrophic character of the pond, manifested both in nutrient concentrations in water and sediments. The biodiversity of benthic macroinvertebrates was much higher in macrophyte patches, and Ephemeroptera – an indicator of good oxygen conditions and low water trophic status – were observed, represented e.g. by Baetidae family.

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Assessment of the effects of climate change on building structures with emphasis on hydrological risks

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Despite the high number of studies dealing with climate change and drought, drought and hydrological risks remain a phenomenon that requires further research. To assess the impacts of climate change, many methodologies have been created so far and methods have been proposed depending on the type of drought or flood risk being investigated. This work deals with the impacts of climate change in the Hornád basin for the period 1961-2020. The time period was divided into three equal time periods namely 1961-1980, 1981-2000 and 2001-2020. The results show that in the Hornád basin in the observed period 2001-2020, daily average annual temperatures in some sub-basins increased by 2°C and average annual precipitation totals increased by 100 to 200 mm. We observe an increase in daily average monthly temperatures in all sub-basins in the summer, namely in the months of June, July and August. We also observe an increase in daily average monthly temperatures in the winter months of November and December. The increase in daily average monthly temperatures was also confirmed by the Mann-Kendal trend test, which confirmed that temperatures are increasing. The average monthly precipitation totals increased in some sub-basins, this was also confirmed by the Mann-Kendal test. Surface runoff in the Hornád basin did not change significantly in the observed period. A more significant increase in surface runoff was in the Spišská Nová Ves station in the period 2001-2020. The obtained results show that the daily evaporation in the Hornád basin has increased.

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Open-source hardware based ROV and USV platforms for lake water quality surveying - outcomes from practical field assessment

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The main aim of the presented work was to develop and test a novel solution based on open-source hardware for the purpose of monitoring water quality in lakes using two different types of remotely operated units: an underwater remotely operated vehicle (ROV) and an unmanned surface vehicle (USV). The vehicles were equipped with an underwater measuring probe that was integrated into their systems. The probe equipped with sensors for basic physical and chemical parameters, i.e. temperature, dissolved oxygen concentration, conductivity, pH and redox potential, was designed and built. In addition, the probe was additionally equipped with a spectrometer that records light intensity in eight spectral channels. The probe's design was based on low-cost modules and sensors available in open-source hardware technology (made by Atlas Scientific and Blue Robotics). The ATmega2560 microcontroller and the Arduino environment were used to control the probe and to record and transmit measurement data. One of the main objectives of the implemented project was to make measurement platforms (based on ROVs and USVs) that will transmit measurement data in real time to an operator located on the shore of the surveyed lake. For this purpose, a simple application for data visualization on a computer screen was developed.

The correctness of sensor readings of selected physico-chemical parameters of water was verified in the field using a professional profiling probe of the WTW brand, while light sensor readings were verified using a profiling radiometer of the BioSpherical brand. The results obtained showed very high agreement of measurement values for temperature, conductivity and light intensity, and satisfactory agreement of results for dissolved oxygen, pH and redox potential values.

Based on the measurements made using ROV and USV platforms, the strengths and weaknesses of each vehicle type were defined in the context of research and monitoring of water quality of lakes and reservoirs. Attention was paid, among other things, to such issues as the potential operating distance of vehicles from the shore or the range of data that can be acquired using ROV and USV platforms.

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Protecting lakes under the art. 139 of the Water Law – rules for lake prioritisation

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The protection area of inland water reservoir is a legal tool introduced under Article 139 of the Water Law Act. This tool enables setting principles for space management and introducing prohibitions and restrictions for works or activities that may cause permanent pollution of soils or waters.

Considering the obligation for protecting lakes against degradation and achieving environmental objectives within a specific timeframe by all waters, the protection area should cover all lakes, although the scope of prohibitions and restrictions may vary greatly depending on the individual situation of each lake. Due to formal, organizational, substantive and economic reasons, this may appear impossible, and even unjustified, to be completed within one 6-year planning cycle. Hence, in the second update of the river basin management plan, the need to develop a procedure for selecting lakes to be included in a protective area was postulated. It should take into account the criteria of effectiveness and justification for introducing such a tool for lakes with specific features and conditions. This action was indicated as a new national measure, common to all lake waterbodies, planned for implementation in 2023.

The aim of the work was to develop a nationally consistent methodology for designating lakes to establish a protective area for inland water reservoirs as referred to in the Article 120 points 2 of the Water Law Act. The proposed methodology was designed based on the pilot study performed on 60 lakes selected so to represent different location, ecological status and catchment conditions. Based on the fixed procedure, 1/3 of them met the criteria for being included in the protection area in the nearest future.

This procedure is intended to be implemented to all 1068 lake waterbodies in Poland to select those, which should be protected under this tool in the first place. The methodology constitutes a decision support system and an element of planning works aimed at developing the third update of water management plans, including the preparation of sets of actions referred to in Article 324 of the Water Law Act.

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Analysis of transport of anthropogenic pollutants along the continuum of the largest Polish rivers

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One of the most important documents in European legislation, establishing a strategy to combat water pollution, is the Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 and Directive 2013/39/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 August 2013 published thirteen years later. These directives contain guidelines for taking actions in the field of water policy, which take into account the proper management of water resources and pay particular attention to the need to monitor a group of dangerous toxic substances constituting water pollution. These documents distinguish a list of 45 priority substances constituting chemical pollutants of surface waters and posing threats that may cause broadly understood toxicity to aquatic organisms, ecosystems and human health. Therefore, according to legal regulations, every effort should be made to limit the emissions of priority substances into water. Among the 45 compounds mentioned, the directives distinguish 21 Priority Hazardous Substances considered as toxic, persistent and susceptible to bioaccumulation, as well as substances or their groups, whose pollution levels reach an alarming level and therefore should be gradually removed from the aquatic environment in order to completely eliminate them.

As the European Environmental Agency (EEA) (2015) report on meeting the requirements of the WFD for river and lake water bodies in individual catchments of large European rivers (including the Vistula and Oder) shows, that more than half of the river and lake waters in Europe have worse condition than defined as *good*. According to the EEA report from 2020, in 2016 as many as 50% of surface water bodies and 25% of groundwater bodies in 28 EU countries and Norway did not achieve good status. Therefore, it is extremely important not only to monitor surfacewater pollution, but also to analyze the transformation of pollution along the river continuum, which allows to provide knowledge about the self-purification potential of large rivers.

The aim of the presented research was to conduct a holistic spatiotemporal analysis of the monitoring and transportation of chemical pollutants, including selected priority substances such as lead, cadmium and benzene, to the Baltic Sea via the largest Polish rivers.

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Absorption of lead and copper on polyethylene microplastics in freshwater

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Microplastics (MPs) are listed among the most serious global environmental issues due to their ubiquitous accumulation in the environment and unknown hazards to biota. It was suggested that MPs can absorb other contaminants such as trace metals and concentrate them to a very high level and thus increase their toxicity. However, the process is still poorly understood, especially mechanisms and controlling factors. The aim of the study was to assess the absorption capacity of pristine and aged MPs for two trace metals (Cu and Pb) in freshwater.

Microplastics were prepared by cutting polyethylene (PE) foil. Part of MPs mass was subjected to aging process. For that, ca. 2 g of MPs was suspended for 10 days in 1 litre of freshwater (collected from a lake) or deionised water (for comparison), the flasks were shaken in a laboratory shaker and kept in sunlight to imitate the natural aging conditions in aquatic reservoirs. Both pristine and aged MPs were characterized using stereomicroscope and SEM. The experiments were performed in freshwater and deionized water spiked with metals at concentration of 200 µg/L. For that, c. 200 mg of MPs (pristine or aged) were suspended in 200 ml of each water spiked with one metal (Cu or Pb) or with mixture of both. Flasks were shaken during 48h. Four ml of water was sampled after 30 min, 1h, 2h, 4h, 8h, 24h, and 48 h. Controls without metals as well as controls without MPs were prepared and treated in the same way. Sampled solutions were acidified with concentrated HNO₃ and metal concentrations were determined using AAS (Perkin Elmer, PinAAcle 900).

The aging process resulted in mechanical damage of the surface of MPs and, in freshwater, adherence of microorganisms. The absorption of metals on MPs fluctuated with time and differed between waters and MPs aging. Generally, aged MPs accumulated more metals than pristine MPs and the absorption of metals was lower in freshwater comparing with deionised water. In some treatments with freshwater the absorption of Pb was equal to the decrease of metal concentration in control. The absorption of Pb was greater in single than in mixed solutions indicating to competitive absorption of Cu and Pb ions. These results show that in natural freshwater MPs might only absorb metals in low concentrations and therefore might not cause threat of poisoning organisms ingesting MPs.

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How do iron coagulants and warming affect the germination rates of aquatic plants?

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The main aim of lake restoration is to improve water quality by decreasing the phosphorus concentration in water, preventing cyanobacterial blooms and recovering macrophytes. One of the most common restoration methods is phosphorus inactivation by using iron sulphate ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) or iron chloride (FeCl_3). It is believed that these chemical substances are harmless to aquatic organisms. However, there is no data about the influence of iron coagulants on aquatic plant germination, especially in a climate-warming scenario. To fill this gap, we conducted germination experiments with sediments from a eutrophic pond (Tancat de la Pipa, *Albufera de València* Natural Park, Spain). The following treatments were established: control (0 mg Fe L⁻¹), low (~4 mg Fe L⁻¹) and high (~11 mg Fe L⁻¹) concentrations of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and FeCl_3 . To simulate the effect of global warming, treatments were under lower (22°C) and higher (27°C) temperatures. Six Petri dishes (Ø 8.8 cm, height 1.5 cm, volume 0.091 L) filled with sediments per treatment were put in containers (34 × 22.5 × 15.5 cm, 8 L) filled with 5 L of dechlorinated tap water. They were incubated in a culture room under constant conditions (14h:10h day:night cycle, temperature 22°C, light intensity ~60 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹). The higher temperature was achieved by setting aquarium heaters in the corresponding containers. The experiment lasted 2 months. The first germling was observed after 7 days. They were collected on day 26 due to the intensive development of filamentous algae in the cultures. Three species germinated: *Chara vulgaris* (dominant, a total of 154 individuals), *C. hispida* (only 1 individual), and *Typha* sp. (4 individuals). The plants were counted and measured (total length), and biomass was determined (dry weight). Subsequent germinated plants were also harvested on the last day of the experiment. Warming significantly increased the number, the length and the biomass of germlings. Overall, the highest doses of coagulants seem to have a negative effect on germination rates. However, once plants germinate, the effect of the coagulants is not so evident. The reaction of other sediments with different diaspore sediment banks might be different. Therefore, considering each lake sediment in particular and conducting germination tests is recommended before applying any coagulant treatment.

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Phototrophic sulfur bacteria as indicators of complex trophic changes in stratified lakes

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Remediation measures in the catchments lead to a decrease in trophic levels in the long term and thus to an improvement in underwater light conditions in lakes. As many stratified lakes still have oxygen-free conditions with hydrogen sulfide formation in the hypolimnion, we postulate that increased euphotic depth favors the formation of deep chlorophyll maxima (DCM) from phototrophic sulfur bacteria (PSB) below the chemocline. To test this hypothesis, we compared data from campaigns at four dimictic lakes in the Scharmützelsee region (1996, 2003 and 2020). In addition to vertical profiles of light, temperature, O₂, H₂S, these also include investigations of the absorption spectra of pigment extracts from different depths, which indicate the presence of PSB through characteristic shifts of the absorption bands and allow a rough quantification of their biomass.

The timing and degree of improvement in the epilimnion varied. While one lake (Tiefer See TIE) has remained almost unchanged at mesotrophic levels since 1996, Scharmützelsee (SCH) and Großer Glubigsee (GGL) have improved since the early 2000s, but Springsee (SPR) only after 2010. In all lakes PSB have been detected since 1996, except SCH only in 2020. Due to reduced primary production in the epilimnion, less detritus was mineralized, resulting in lower sulfide concentrations that shifted the DCM to greater depths. Despite the downwards shift of the chemocline by 4m in GGL, 6m in SPR and 7m in SCH, the biomass of PSB was rather higher compared to 1996. An increased BChla to BChle ratio indicated a species shift within the PSB due to improved underwater light conditions and reduced H₂S concentrations. Thus, we were able to detect complex and trophic relevant changes in the plankton communities below the metalimnion, which are unfortunately not included in the assessment of EU Water Framework Directive. Our results support the notion that meta- and hypolimnetic communities are hotspots for biodiversity and microbial metabolic processes and thus deserve more attention, also in long-term studies, to improve our understanding of global changes on lake ecosystems.

Stoichiometric flexibility of *Myriophyllum spicatum* in response to environmental variability

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Despite efforts to reduce nutrient inputs, eutrophication continues to disrupt biogeochemical cycles and destabilize freshwater food webs. This study investigates the stoichiometric responses of *Myriophyllum spicatum* to varied environmental conditions in different lake types. *M. spicatum* specimens were collected from lakes ranging from softwater *Lobelia*-dominated to hypertrophic with degraded flora. These lakes varied significantly in macro- and micronutrient content in both water and sediments. Using ecological stoichiometry, we analyzed the relationship between nutrient availability in water and sediments and the elemental composition of *M. spicatum*'s leaves, shoots, and roots. Data were analyzed using a Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) to consider the combined effects of water and sediment nutrients. Findings showed significant influences of sediment composition on carbon (C), phosphorus (P), and zinc (Zn) content in *M. spicatum*, while nutrients in the water column had no significant correlations. Leaves exhibited C and P content flexibility, negatively correlating with sediment C and P levels. Leaves and roots had the highest nitrogen (N) content, indicating simultaneous nutrient uptake from water and sediment. The study highlighted distinct nutrient allocation strategies of *M. spicatum*: leaves had higher N content, facilitating efficient photosynthesis under low light. Roots predominantly accumulate micronutrients like Fe, Zn, and Cu. Stems allocated higher C and P, supporting rapid growth and reproduction. These findings emphasize sediment as a primary nutrient source for *M. spicatum*, influencing its stoichiometric composition and growth strategies. The study underscores ecological stoichiometry's role in understanding the adaptive strategies of macrophytes to varying environmental conditions and its broader implications for freshwater ecosystems' conservation and restoration amid climate change challenges.

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The ecological stoichiometry of bloom-forming cyanobacteria under different climate change scenarios

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Cyanobacteria intensify their growth under warmer and carbon dioxide-richer conditions, and hence, these prokaryotes can form denser blooms and maintain higher biomass in nutrient-rich ecosystems. The interplay between climate change and elemental balance shapes cyanobacteria communities, posing a compelling ecological puzzle. Ecological stoichiometry principles may be crucial, yet few studies have explicitly connected these factors. In this study, we compared nutrient (C, N, P) uptake and storage in bloom-forming cyanobacteria (*Aphanizomenon gracile*, *Cuspidothrix issatschenkoi*, *Raphidiopsis raciborski*) growing for over 50 days in the nutrient-rich medium under ambient conditions (430 ppm CO₂, 20°C) and elevated CO₂ and temperature (1200 ppm CO₂, 26°C). Nutrient analysis revealed substantial variability in nutrient uptake efficiency among studied strains. Elevated temperature and CO₂ concentration accelerated the growth of all studied strains and increased the production of heterocytes in heterocytous cyanobacteria. A special case was *C. issatschenkoi*, in which climate warming caused a significant increase in the C:N ratio and decreased C:P. Phosphorus emerged as the more limiting nutrient compared to nitrogen, and the key regulating factor was the presence of heterocytes – a hotter and richer CO₂ atmosphere, more heterocytes produced, and consequently, more nitrogen stored in cyanobacterial cells. To conclude, our experiments revealed that temperature and CO₂ elevation influence the C:nutrients ratios in cyanobacteria, which may consequently affect their nutritional value for consumers. This effect is probably highly species- and strain-specific. Enhanced integration of field and laboratory studies is essential to discern changes in stoichiometry that dictate the functioning of entire food webs.

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Hydrological modelling of the peatlands to understand their effects on the flash floods

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The mountainous and bordering area, within the North-West Region of Romania, integrates numerous peatlands, with a humid and cool climate, areas located in the formation areas of liquid runoff, which is frequently torrential. This study is focusing on the peatlands' effects on the discharge of an extraordinary flood, generated by a computational rainfall with a 1% probability of occurrence. The case studies are the 10 representative peatlands analyzed within the NWPEAT project, located in the aforementioned geographic region. The analysis of their efficiency in mitigating the maximum torrential runoff **(1)**, as well as the evaluation of the raising effect for the drainage area through ecological dams made of local materials towards an additional mitigation of the same phenomenon **(2)**, represent extremely important results, both for the human environment, as well as for the natural one, located downstream of peatlands.

As actions preceding the modeling, we have made a detailed analysis of the field sites, regarding their spatial distribution by morphological units, water balance indicators, the analysis of runoff and aridity coefficients, the study of the basins' shape in order to identify the ones capable of becoming torrent generators.

In the case of the first chapter, there were two scenarios, applied for each peatland, considering their surface in two variants: a natural, effective one, occupied by the current ecosystem and a second one in which the nature of its surface is identical to that of the slope, so the wetland ecosystem is missing. The results are more than conclusive, the current peatland surface is bringing a two-fold reduction of the maximum effluent flow, compared to the second variant.

For the second chapter, the two scenarios, were applied involving the modeling of the rain-runoff process with the presence of the natural dam and respectively without it. The results differ from one case to another, observing a reduction of the maximum runoff of 70% in the case of the Iaz peatland, 40% in the case of the Manta Lake peatland and only 8% in the case of the Ic Ponor bogs. The difference between the three chosen representative cases is the different manifestation of some natural factors, among which are the peatland surface, the area and the shape of the slope basin, the degree of coverage and development stages

of vegetation layer within the basin, the different spatial distribution of the sites according with the directions of water flow. The present study validates the extremely important effect of peatlands on mitigation the torrential runoff, encouraging the massive rehabilitation and protection of this type of ecosystems in the highland area of runoff formation, with the effect of protecting water catchment areas (confluence areas), frequently occupied by extended human habitats.

The impact of salinization on freshwater ecosystems

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Defined nine planetary boundaries (PB) within which humanity can operate safely did not mention freshwater salinization per se, but it is nonetheless related with those boundaries: climate change, biological diversity lose, biogeochemical nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) cycle, global freshwater use and chemical pollution. Increasing chloride concentrations have been observed in rivers and lakes. Although some of the effects of freshwater salinization (FS) are well recognized, but the impact of anthropogenic FS on freshwater ecosystems remains unclear, especially since a number of cumulative interactions exist between FS and PB and other anthropogenic activities. In some cases, human activities associated with PBs can serve as sources of salinization, while in others, salinization can increase the chance of exceeding safe limits; it is also possible that both can occur.

Road salt, one source of salinization, increases chemical pollution of water by releasing pollutants like heavy metals from soils and storage in sediments. In addition, global freshwater use increases salinization through anthropopressure. Taken together, the anthropogenic impact leads to FS, which exacerbates other negative consequences of human impact, and deteriorates surface water quality. While scientific interest in FS has increased during the last two decades, our understanding of the ecological and evolutionary impact of FS remains incomplete from the molecular to global scale. There has been limited focus on the functional, spatial and trophic consequences of FS, and only few long-term studies exist. Increased salinization initiates various chemical reactions and nutrient cycles, thus influencing water quality and the ecohydrological reaction to it.

Zooplankton is also affected by FS. Knowledge about the impact of FS on its functioning is important, because of the important role it plays in the food web in water ecosystems, by controlling the amount of phytoplankton (top-down effect in algal blooms reduction). However, greater knowledge of the factors affecting the hatching and growth of zooplankton is needed to maintain adequate surface water quality. Our research give new information about the effect of road salt (NaCl) on the hatching success of *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus*. The number of hatchings decreased with increasing NaCl concentration for *T. platyurus*, and decreased rapidly after a crucial value of 7 600 mg NaCl/L for *D. magna*. At the second hatching (eggs washed after first incubation and put into standard freshwater), *D. magna* demonstrated a low hatching rate regardless of NaCl concentration, while most *T. platyurus* hatchings were observed at the highest NaCl

concentration (15 200 mg/L) with sum of both hatching similar to lower concentration. We also evaluated acute toxicity of seven de-icing salts, sold as an “eco-friendly” alternative, on four zooplankton species *Ceriodaphnia dubia* (Ceriodaphtokit), *Daphnia magna* (Daphtoxkit), *Brachionus calyciflorus* (Rotoxkit) and *Thamnocephalus platyurus* (Thamnotoxkit). 24-h EC₅₀ evaluation showed that only solid CH₃COOK was less toxic for all tested species than NaCl. The other tested deicing salts had similar or even higher toxicity, with CaCl₂, MgCl₂ and liquid CH₃COOK being significantly more toxic for all species than NaCl. Important part of our work was to investigate the effect of chloride ion concentration and interpond environmental variability on zooplankton density. Study was conducted for three years in four urban ponds with different level of road salt infow. Zooplankton density depended on ponds characteristics, although the density of all zooplankton groups demonstrated clear negative correlation with chloride and a positive correlation with potassium.

While many gaps still remain in our understanding of the ecological and evolutionary consequences of freshwater salinization, our current state of knowledge indicates clear connections with planetary boundaries and harmful aglal blooms, like Oder catatropy, where *Prymnesium parvum* caused one of the greatest ecological disasters in the recent history of European rivers. The issue of FS demands greater attention from scientists (to fill knowledge gaps), stakeholders and practitioners. It not only impacts freshwater ecosystems, but also threatens the maintenance of good water quality, which is necessary for ensuring human well-being and protecting ecosystem services.

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Decade-long investigations of limnological processes and modern sedimentation at Lake Żabińskie, northeast Poland

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Knowledge about how seasonal meteorological conditions and related limnological processes influence sedimentation dynamics in lakes is still limited. Here, we present a dataset of a decade-long monitoring project of Lake Żabińskie. This hardwater and eutrophic lake in northeast Poland contains annually laminated (varved) sediments that form a unique archive of past environmental variability. The overall monitoring program was designed to assess relationships among meteorological conditions, limnological processes, and modern sedimentation and to answer the question of whether meteorological and limnological phenomena can be precisely tracked with varves. We applied regular measurements of the lake water physical and chemical characteristics as well as seasonal variability in sediment fluxes. The combination of ultra-high-resolution μ XRF and hyperspectral imaging (HSI) techniques allowed us to detect sub-seasonal variability of biogeochemical data in the topmost sediments. Next, we compared this dataset with meteorological data, water column characteristics, and modern sedimentation data. Mass accumulation rates and sediment composition in sediment trap samples were well reproduced in the sediment record, i.e. in varve thickness and structure. That was particularly seen in multiple deposition of calcite laminae after colder and more windy periods during summer stratification. Distinct manganese (Mn) peaks in sediments are indicative of holomixis events which tend to occur during relatively long and cold springs or in fall/early winter due to the late formation of ice-cover on the lake. Our findings confirm that comprehensive observations of limnological parameters combined with sediment trapping and high-resolution analyses of sediment cores enable tracking the influence of meteorological conditions on varve formation and climate signal preservation in sediments. The dataset is archived at <https://doi.org/10.34808/w8w7-9x34>.

Environmental changes and human impact on landslide Zawadowskie Pond (Gorce Mts., South Poland)

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We present a continuous record of Late Holocene sediments spanning the last ~6000 cal yr BP from landslide Zawadowski Pond in the Polish Outer Carpathians. Our aim was to identify the main environmental changes in past, also related to human activity. The landslide zone was successively formed by several mass movement generations induced by headward erosion. Increased mass movements activity in the Gorce Mts relate to cold and humid periods of the Holocene. This cooling period has been linked with glacier advances in the Alps. In the course of its development, the Zawadowski Pond passed through several phases. The water level changed multiple times reflecting climate change. Here we focus on how the diatom assemblages have been affected by climatic and anthropogenic induced environmental changes.

To determine how these changes affected diatom biodiversity, a 5-meter-long sediment core was examined. The sediment layers contain perfectly preserved diatom shells, present in large amount in all core layers. Among clearly dominant diatoms are *Staurosira*, *Staurosirella* and *Fragilaria* taxa, mainly present in oligo- to mesotrophic waters. The first shift in the dominance ratios were detected around 2700 years ago and corresponds with the formation of Iwanowski Pond, 100 m away from Zawadowski Pond. Until then the assemblages mostly consist of *Staurosirella mutabilis*, *S. neopinnata*, *Fragilaria rhabdosoma*, *Staurosira binodis* and *Achnantheidium minutissimum*, the diatom taxa predominantly common in circumneutral to alkaline, waters with low to moderate electrolyte contents. The next shifts are c.a. 500 cal yr BP and 1500 cal.yr AD. In the first shift, *Staurosirella neopinnata* and *S. mutabilis* disappeared, while *Staurosira neoproducta* appeared in large numbers. *Staurosira neoproducta* occurs in circumneutral waters with higher electrolyte content. The observed diatoms that co-occur with it prefer calcium-bicarbonate enriched, mesotrophic, alkaline conditions. In samples from the highest part of the core, clearly predominate *Staurosirella mutabilis*, *Staurosira venter* and *S. construens*. *Staurosira construens*, which occurred only in the last phase, is known from more or less calcareous waterbodies, oligo- to eutrophic, β-mesosaprobic waters; also in electrolyte poor, circumneutral waters. These changes are related to temperature, water availability variation and change in the composition of tree species in the surrounding forest.

Microscopic invertebrates on snow patches

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Because of high accumulation during winter and melting during the spring, snow influences adjacent ecosystems serving as a source of water, but also nutrients. In addition, snow is a unique and ephemeral environment during spring and summer; the snow surface is a borderline between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Snow patches maintain a film of water on their surface when the temperature is above zero, providing a colonizable habitat for primary producers like algae, decomposers like bacteria and fungi, and highest trophic level consumers such as invertebrates. The colour of the snow surface changes into red, green, golden-brown or orange due to snow algae blooming over the melt season. Although the diversity of algae and effects of snow algae pigmentation on the snow albedo are discussed in the literature, knowledge of metazoans such as microscopic invertebrates is scarce. The presence of invertebrates can potentially influence nutrient availability for snow-adjacent ecosystems as they can control primary producers and decomposers on the snow surface. To fill this knowledge gap we collected samples from different snow surfaces (clean, dusty and algae-covered) in the Pyrenees, Alps, Baltic States, Central Norway and Svalbard. Invertebrates were identified by microscopic and DNA-based approaches. Collectively, we found representatives of Tardigrada, Rotifera, Nematoda, Acari and Collembola. Preliminary data indicates that invertebrates found on the snow could be grouped as (i) wind-blown, accidental faunal elements (e.g. Acari), (ii) limno-terrestrial taxa which use snow as temporal habitat (e.g. Rotifera), and (iii) specialists which inhabit both glacial and snow ecosystems (Tardigrada). The intestine contents of some of these invertebrates indicate that they feed on snow algae.

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Biodiversity and Fate of Glacial Organisms

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Although lifeless at first glance, glacier surface is inhabited by myriad organisms representing all trophic levels and kingdoms of life. The surface of glaciers worldwide offers various lotic and lentic environments for ubiquitous microscopic, yet awaiting discovery life forms. Cryoconite holes (small reservoirs embodied within glacial ice), bedieres (supraglacial streams) or surface ice of weathering crust with the active aquifer, are among the most important habitats for glacial psychrophiles. Due to global warming, the most endangered glacial ecosystems are valley glaciers in polar regions and ice masses in the low latitude mountain ranges. Many of those glacial ecosystems will likely disappear by the end of the century along with their unique biota. The main aims of our study are i) cataloguing the diversity of eukaryotes in glacial habitats, ii) test their physiological capability to tolerate higher than on glacier surface temperatures, and iii) investigate their historical biogeography with a special focus on warm episodes and interglacial cycles. We found that glaciers are inhabited worldwide by rotifers and tardigrades. Tardigrades are glacier-specific species while rotifers represent both glacial-obligate species or those that inhabit glacial and non-glacial habitats. Representatives of both survive higher than on-ice surface temperatures but die at specific thresholds. Preliminary studies on eukaryotic green algae and cyanobacteria indicate the presence of both specialists and opportunistic species on glaciers. Finally, historical biogeography indicates that some glacial taxa survived previous warm periods in glacial refugia. The entire loss of mountainous glaciers will trigger the extinction of glacier specialists characterised by low ecological tolerance.

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